

Uncertainty analysis of IceCube instrument to enhance accuracy of specific surface area measurements

Leena Leppänen^{a,b,*}

^a Finnish Meteorological Institute, Space and Earth Observation Centre, Tähteläntie 62, 99600 Sodankylä, Finland

^b University of Lapland, Arctic Centre, Pohjoisranta 4, 96200 Rovaniemi, Finland

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ABSTRACT

The specific surface area (SSA) is a measure of the snow microstructure and can be determined using an instrument called IceCube. IceCube measures the reflectance from surface of a snow sample with a 1310 nm infrared laser. In this study, the uncertainties associated with IceCube measurements of SSA were analyzed in two locations: Sodankylä, Finland and Queen Maud Land, Antarctica. The study tests the repeatability of the measurements by measuring several samples from the same height of a homogenous snowpack. Additionally, snow samples were rotated to find minimum and maximum reflectance values to test the uncertainty related to the direction of the sample under the laser. The study also observed the uncertainty related to potential melting of the sample in warm conditions due to slow measurement process. The study resulted that the highest uncertainty is related to the sampling process. Overall, this study provides insights into the uncertainties associated with IceCube measurements of SSA, which will improve the precision and reliability of future measurements.

1. Introduction

The specific surface area (SSA) is a critical parameter that describes the microstructure of snow, and it has become increasingly important with advances in measurement technology. One widely-used method for measuring SSA is to use infrared reflectance, which has been shown to be related to SSA in previous studies (Domine et al., 2006; Gallet et al., 2009). Transportable instruments, such as the commercial IceCube instrument manufactured by A2 Photonic Sensors (Zuanon, 2013), have made it possible to measure SSA in the field. The IceCube is constructed with similar principle and the same components as DUFIS (Dual Frequency Integrating Sphere for Snow SSA measurement) which was the first instrument measuring SSA with 1310 nm reflectance (Gallet et al., 2009). The IceCube instrument has been used for over a decade to measure SSA in a variety of environments, including Alpine and taiga snowpacks, as well as Greenland and Antarctica (Calonne et al., 2020; Lemmetyinen et al., 2018; Jäkel et al., 2021; Carlsen et al., 2017).

Currently, there are only a limited number of studies that investigate the uncertainty sources of IceCube measurements or compare them with other SSA measurement methods. For example, Calonne et al. (2020) found that compared to X-ray micro computed tomography observations of SSA, IceCube systematically overestimated SSA values by about 1.3

times. Martin and Schneebeli (2023) demonstrated that there is a systematic difference of 20–52% between the methods for snow with SSA values ranging from 5 to 25 m²/kg. They revealed that this difference is snow type-dependent and arises from the IceCube sampling procedure, which causes the formation of small grains on the sample surface through the mechanical destruction of smoothing with a spatula. Leppänen and Kontu (2018) tested the repeatability of IceCube SSA measurements in Sodankylä, Finland, and found that the relative standard deviation (RSTD) of repeated measurements of the same sample was 2%, and the RSTD of precipitation particles and depth hoar compacted with a spatula to different densities was below 3%. Gallet et al. (2009) reported that the DUFIS exhibited systematic and random errors at 10%. Another reflectance-based instrument using integrating sphere, based also on DUFIS, InfraRed Integrating Sphere (IRIS), was reported by Montpetit et al. (2012) to exhibit an error of 7% compared to X-ray micro computed tomography. Furthermore, Dumont et al. (2021) observed that optical methods (DUFIS and ASSAP) consistently yielded higher SSA values when compared to X-ray micro computed tomography.

To expand upon these findings, this study examines the uncertainties of IceCube SSA measurements for taiga snowpack in Sodankylä, Finland during the spring of 2020, as well as for Antarctic snow in Queen Maud

* Corresponding author at: Finnish Meteorological Institute, Space and Earth Observation Centre, Tähteläntie 62, 99600 Sodankylä, Finland.

E-mail address: leena.leppanen@fmi.fi.

Land during the summer of 2022–2023 as part of the Finnish Antarctic research program FINNARP 2022 expedition.

2. Methods

IceCube measures the hemispherical reflectance of a 1310 nm infrared laser from the surface of the snow sample (Fig. 1a), using a measurement principle similar to DUFISSS (Gallet et al., 2009). The snow sample is extracted from the snowpack and placed in a sample holder using either a spatula or a sampler with a piston (Fig. 1c and d). The sample is then placed to a snow port under the laser and the voltage (mV) value is recorded, which is later converted to SSA using software that employs calibration data and polynomial fit. The polynomial fit is based on calibration measurements made with DUFISSS and methane absorption method (Gallet et al., 2009). To derive the polynomial fit for

SSA determination, the Discrete Ordinates Radiative Transfer Program for a Multi-Layered Plane-Parallel Medium (DISORT) model was fitted to the calibration measurements. IceCube is calibrated with DUFISSS and identical polynomial fit is used also for IceCube. A more detailed description of the sampling procedure can be found in Leppänen et al. (2016) and in Leppänen and Kontu (2018).

Before and/or after the measurement, the instrument is calibrated using Spectralon targets with differing tint (Fig. 1b). In addition, the dark current is also measured for the calibration. Instrument calibration is needed for calculating two optical parameters, the laser diode collimation and the hemispherical reflectance of the sphere wall, as well as the gain of the electronics and an offset caused by electronic or optical noise (Gallet et al., 2009). These parameters are essential for converting reflectance values to SSA (Zuanon, 2013). The calibration equation, employed for this purpose, is presented in Gallet et al. (2009). The initial

a)

c)

b)

d)

Fig. 1. a) IceCube instrument, b) calibration standards, c) sampling with the piston sampler, d) smoothing sample surface with the spatula. Credit: FMI and FINNARP 2022.

calibration is performed after approximately a 10-min stabilization period following the instrument has been switched on. In the standard measurement procedure in Sodankylä, both initial (before) and final (after) calibrations are conducted. It is advisable to repeat the calibration process if the temperature changes by 10 °C, since fluctuations in the instrument's internal temperature can impact the calibration result. However, only one calibration value can be utilized in the software at a time.

Uncertainties of IceCube instrument SSA measurements were evaluated during the SnowAPP project field campaign in Sodankylä in spring 2020. The measurement site was in a wetland (N67.367070°, E26.651170°) where the snow is typically quite homogeneous (López-Moreno et al., 2020). In western Queen Maud Land, IceCube uncertainty measurements were made during the LAS3R project field campaign as part of the FINNARP 2022 expedition on November 29th, 2022 at S73.1059°, W13.1629°, December 16th, 2022 at S73.1059°, W013.5689°, and on January 12th, 2023 at S73.1060°, W013.1631°, all located at a glacier approximately 10 km from the Finnish Aboa station. The instrument used in Antarctica was purchased in 2021, while the one used in Sodankylä was purchased in 2012.

The uncertainty associated with the orientation of the sample under the laser was assessed by rotating the snow samples to determine both the minimum and maximum reflectance values. The repeatability of the IceCube instrument SSA measurements was evaluated by measuring several snow samples from the same height of the snowpack. The impact of potential melting on the sample due to slow measurement process was also observed. The most comprehensive measurements to define uncertainties were conducted on 16 and 22 April 2020 in Sodankylä and on 29 November and 16 December 2022 in Antarctica. Additionally, measurements taken on 18 March 2020, 6 April 2020, 30 April 2020, and 5 May 2020 in Sodankylä included some measurements of repeatability, while the measurements taken on 12 January 2023 in Antarctica included potential melting of the samples in warm conditions. Sampling was conducted for certain layers in Antarctica and for every 3 cm in Sodankylä, although one sample may include snow grains from more than one layer. However, the top 3 cm of the snow surface was also sampled in Antarctica.

In addition, stratigraphy was observed with grain type, grain size, hardness and wetness. Hardness was tested with a scale from fist, four fingers, one finger, pen, knife to ice (1–6). Wetness scale used was from dry, moist, wet, very wet to soaked (1–5). Snow classification was based on Fierz et al. (2009). For wet snow SSA (SSA_{wet}) calculation is applied an eq. (1) from Gallet et al. (2014).

$$SSA_{wet} = 0.994^{\wedge} (SSA + 0.5 \text{ m}^2/\text{kg}) \quad (1)$$

The equation was applied for all samples where wetness was defined as at least to 3 (wet).

3. Results

Sodankylä sampling included precipitation particles, rounded grains, melt formations, and depth hoar crystals. In Antarctica, the grains in the snow pits used for this study were rounded and precipitation particles. Stratigraphy data, including grain type, grain size, wetness, and hardness, for 16 April 2020, 22 April 2020, 29 November 2022, and 16 December 2022, are presented in Fig. 2. The locations of the SSA measurements are indicated by green, blue, and yellow bars, representing the melting, repeating sampling, and rotating sample, respectively.

Repeatability was also evaluated with surface snow measurements on four additional days. On 18 March 2020, the surface consisted of 1.5 cm layers of soft (fist), small (0.5 mm), and moist precipitation particles on top, with a hard crust layer below. On 6 April 2020, the surface had soft (fist) and dry rounded grains, with an average grain size of 0.5–0.75 mm. On 30 April 2020, the surface had dry snow with a very thin layer of precipitation particles (grain size 0.5 mm) on top, and a hard (knife)

melt formation layer with a grain size of 2.25 mm below it. On 5 May 2020, the surface had dry to moist melt formations (polycrystals, crust, and clusters) with an average grain size of approximately 2 mm. The topmost 2 cm was hard (pen) and the snow below was softer (4 fingers). In the melting test conducted on 12 January 2023, in Antarctica, the snow was dry and hard (pen-knife) and had rounded grains with a grain size of 1–1.5 mm.

The uncertainties associated with rotating samples under the laser, repeating measurements at the same height, potential melting in warm air temperatures, and calibration (whether done before or after the measurements), were all investigated. The standard deviation (STD) and relative standard deviation (RSTD) for each type of uncertainty are presented in Table 1, and further analysis of these uncertainties is provided in the following sections.

3.1. Rotating sample under the laser

To assess the uncertainty related to the direction of the sample under the laser, samples were rotated and the minimum and maximum values obtained during rotation were recorded. For many samples, three values were recorded: the original measurement, as well as the minimum and maximum values obtained from rotating the sample. All of these values were included in the analysis. In some cases, the first measurement value recorded was smaller or larger than the minimum or maximum reached during the rotation.

In Sodankylä on 16 April 2020, calibration after measurements was used. Five samples including crust on 16 April were left out from the following analysis. SSA values from 35 samples on 16 April 2020 and 17 samples on 22 April 2020 were used. Differences between minimum and maximum values varied between 0.2 and 3.3 m²/kg. On 16 April STD was largest (1.4 m²/kg) for rounded grains with hand hardness scale “pen”, and the largest RSTD were for depth hoar (11.0%) and for brown colored and wet snow at bottom of the snowpack (9.7%). On 22 April, STD was largest for surface snow (1.65 m²/kg), and large RSTD were for hard snow from layer interface (21.6%), for surface snow (20.5%), and for wet snow (11.8%).

In Antarctica, rotated SSA was measured from 18 samples on 29 November 2022 and from 11 samples on 16 December. Differences between minimum and maximum values varied between 0.1 and 1.2 m²/kg.

3.2. Repeating sampling at the same height

The repeatability of the measurements was assessed by collecting samples from the same height multiple times. The samples were taken in close proximity to each other to minimize spatial variability of snow properties. The analysis included measurements taken below 3 cm under the snow surface. For some samples, three values were recorded: the original measurement, as well as the minimum and maximum values obtained after rotating the sample described in section 3.1. Whenever possible, maximum values were utilized to minimize uncertainty arising from the sample's orientation under the laser, discussed in the preceding section. Samples including crust, collected on 16 April from three different heights were excluded from the analysis.

In Sodankylä, measurements were repeated at seven heights on 16 April 2020 (3–5 samples for each height) and two heights on 22 April 2020 (2–3 samples for each height), encompassing various snow types. For 16 April, data with after calibration was used. STD varied between 0.2 and 1.8 m²/kg, average between 5.7 and 32.7 m²/kg and RSTD between 2.3 and 29.1%. RSTD was largest (29.1%) for wet snow on 22 April 2020.

In Antarctica, measurements were repeated for three heights on 29 November and 16 December, with four samples taken from each height. Before calibration was used because it was performed closer proximity to the measurements. STD varied between 0.3 and 1.7 m²/kg, average between 17.2 and 29.1 m²/kg and RSTD between 1.3 and 7.2%.

a) 16 April 2020

b) 22 April 2020

Fig. 2. Stratigraphy with grain size, grain type, wetness and hardness for a) 16 April 2020, b) 22 April 2020, c) 29 November 2022 and d) 16 December 2022. Color bars in the middle indicates location of the samples: melting in warm temperature (green), repeating sampling (blue) and rotating sample under laser (yellow). Grain types are indicated with colors in the left column: precipitation particles (green), rounded grains (light red), melt forms (red), melt-freeze crust (red with black stripes), faceted crystals (light blue), depth hoar (blue), ice formations (cyan). Original visualizations were made with niViz tool. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

To assess the uncertainty originating from sample preparation, measurements were taken on 18 March 2020, in Sodankylä. Two to four samples were collected from four different heights, including the snow surface. All produced samples, including those that were unsuccessful due to uneven smoothness or incorrect surface levels, were included in the analysis to observe effects of improper sampling. STD varied between 1.5 and 12.1 m²/kg, average varied between 14.6 and 38.4 m²/kg and RSTD varied between 9.9 and 43.9%.

3.3. Sampling the surface snow

Measuring the surface snow is one of the most challenging aspects of using IceCube due to the presence of hard crusts or soft precipitated particles. To test the repeatability of surface sampling, the samples were taken several times close to each other.

The sampler provided with the instrument was used for sampling in Sodankylä. When samples were successful, cutting or adding more snow with the spatula were not needed. On 18 March 2020, the surface snow was sampled five times. Two of the measurements were successful with average of 40.9 m²/kg and with 0.3 m²/kg (0.7%) difference. On 16 April 2020, the surface snow was sampled five times, and STD was 5.8 m²/kg, average 34.9 m²/kg and RSTD 16.6%. On 22 April 2020, the surface snow was measured with four samples. Minimum and maximum values from rotating samples were included to the analysis. Three of the samples were successful with STD of 1.1 m²/kg, average of 8.3 m²/kg and RSTD of 13.5%. On 30 April 2020 the surface snow was measured three times and two successful measurements had average of 13.3 m²/kg and 0.1 m²/kg (0.008%) difference. On 5 May 2020 the surface snow was measured three times and two successful measurements were 2.8 m²/kg without any difference.

Additionally, unsuccessful samples were also analyzed to determine the impact of challenging sampling procedure. On 18 March 2020, a sample with ~1 mm too high surface level had 7.4 m²/kg (18.2%) higher SSA value. A sample with cracked surface had 5.0 m²/kg (12.1%) lower SSA value. On 6 April 2020 the surface snow was measured three times. None of the samples were perfect, since two of them were too low and more soft snow was added to the top with a spatula for one of the samples. STD was 1.8 m²/kg, average 30.6 m²/kg and RSTD was 5.8%. On 22 April 2020, one of the samples was a bit higher than the sample holder and had the smallest SSA value with difference of 1.7 m²/kg (20.5%). On 30 April 2020, one of the samples was too low, and its difference to the successful samples was 3 m²/kg (22.5%). On 5 May 2020, one of the samples was too low. Difference to two other samples was 0.4 m²/kg (14.2%).

In Antarctica, surface snow had light precipitation particles on 29 November 2022 when surface snow was collected with spatula to sample holder for five samples. STD was 1.2 m²/kg, average was 49.8 m²/kg and RSTD was 2.5%.

3.4. Potential melting in warm conditions

When air temperature approaches 0 °C and solar radiation is intense, the surface of the snow sample begins to melt. This effect is more pronounced near the edges of the sample due to the black sample holder. The objective was to investigate how the slow sampling procedure might impact measurements. The effect of potential sample melting on SSA values was assessed by waiting a few minutes in warm temperature and repeating the measurements. During this period, the samples were not shaded. It is assumed that the samples can be regarded as wet after two minutes, and eq. (1) for wet snow SSA is applied.

The samples were also rotated to obtain the minimum and maximum values, except on 12 January 2023 in Antarctica. Table 1 utilizes maximum values, where available, to minimize uncertainty arising from the sample's orientation under the laser, discussed in detail in chapter 3.1. The calculation involves the initial and the final measurement of a certain waiting period.

On 16 April 2020, samples were taken from depth hoar in +0.4 °C air temperature. Minimum values decreased from 7.3 to 7.2 m²/kg (1.4%) and maximum values remained in 9.4 m²/kg in four minutes. On 22 April 2020, in four minutes in +2 °C air temperature, minimum values decreased from 4.1 to 3.7 m²/kg (10.8%) and maximum values decreased from 4.9 to 4.6 m²/kg (6.5%) for wet snow including rounded grains and wet clustered rounded crystals. During six minutes in the same temperature, minimum values increased from 3.5 to 3.6 m²/kg (2.9%) and maximum from 5.5 to 5.3 m²/kg (3.8%) for rounded polycrystals and rounded grains.

In Antarctica on 29 November 2022, during two minutes minimum values decreased from 22.2 to 22.1 m²/kg (0.5%) and maximum values remained as 22.4 m²/kg for rounded grains in 0 °C air temperature. On 12 January 2023, during melting of eight minutes values increased from 22.5 m²/kg to 22.6 m²/kg (0.4%) for rounded grains of surface sample in +3 °C air temperature. Moreover, rounded grains from depth of 15 cm had increase from 16.1 m²/kg to 16.4 m²/kg (1.9%) during melting of four minutes in the same temperature.

3.5. Calibration

In both Sodankylä and Antarctica, calibrations made before and after the measurements were compared for the 16 April 2020 in Sodankylä and nine measurement sessions in Antarctica. IceCube software rated both calibrations in Sodankylä as “excellent”, which means that the calibration curve has excellent fit to the calibration points. Success of the calibration process is related to clean and unbroken calibration standards. The maximum difference in SSA between the calibrations was 0.3 m²/kg, which was for surface snow, and maximum difference in percentage was 1.7%, for depth hoar. Results include 118 samples, including rotated samples and repeated melting measurements after a certain time. The values were typically larger when the calibration made after the measurements was used. In Antarctica, all calibrations were also rated as “excellent.” The maximum difference in SSA between the calibrations was 0.4 m²/kg and 1.7% in 82 samples, including rotated samples and repeated melting measurements after a certain time. Again, the values were typically larger with the after calibration.

4. Discussion

In this study, various error sources associated with SSA measurements using the IceCube instrument were examined. The research focused on investigating uncertainties arising from the sampling and measurement procedure, as well as the impact of the calibration. Measurements were conducted in two diverse locations: Sodankylä, Finland and Queen Maud Land, Antarctica. It is noteworthy that with the exception of the measurements made for testing sample preparation on 18 March 2020, all measurements were conducted by the author, thus eliminating variability related to the observer.

In comparing the uncertainties in Sodankylä and Antarctica, this study reveals that the uncertainty of IceCube measurements in the Antarctic snow was generally better than in the taiga snowpack in Sodankylä (Table 1), especially when considering the RSTD. This disparity can be explained by the fact that the SSA values of the observed

c) 29 November 2022

d) 16 December 2022

Fig. 2. (continued).

snow types were smaller in Finland than in Antarctica. Likewise, [Domine et al. \(2006\)](#) noted that experimental errors tend to be higher for low SSA values. Additionally, the ease of sampling rounded grains with correct level and smooth surface, prevalent in Antarctica, contrasts with the challenges posed by other grain types such as depth hoar, frequently

observed in Sodankylä. Additionally, while the STD values were closer to each other than RSTD values, measurements in Antarctica still showed more favorable results. For this study, values obtained from resampling the same height and rotation are the most comparable since the melting test was performed at different temperatures and surface

Table 1

Average STD and RSTD, and the maximum RSTD in parenthesis, are provided for measurements conducted in Sodankylä and in western Queen Maud Land.

Type of uncertainty	Finland			Antarctica		
	STD (m ² /kg)	RSTD (%)	Number of samples	STD (m ² /kg)	RSTD (%)	Number of samples
Rotation (max-min)	0.45	5.35 (21.6)	52	0.13	0.48 (1.03)	29
Resampling the same height	0.73	6.93 (29.1)	30 (2–5 samples from 8 layers)	0.93	3.51 (7.2)	28 (4 samples from 7 layers)
Resampling to test sample preparation	7.42	28.49 (44.0)	4	–	–	0
Resampling surface	2.93	12.1 (18.9)	23 (3–5 samples from 6 days)	1.25	2.51	5
Melting (original and after time period)	2 min	0.03	3	0.11	0.64	3
					(1.03)	
	4 min	0.09	3	0.09	0.53	2
					(0.93)	
	6 min	0.12	1	0.23	1.01	1
	8 min	–	0	0.03	0.14	1
Calibration (difference)	0.06	0.32	118	0.06	0.004	82

resampling had a low number of samples in Antarctica. In addition, the calibration test produced similar values for both regions but RSTD was negligible for Antarctica. It's worth noting that the uncertainty associated with sample rotation is linked to snow properties, while the uncertainty arising from repeated sampling is tied to sample preparation and spatial variability, and these uncertainties are not related to instrumental errors.

The study found that the largest source of uncertainty was related to the sample preparation. Errors in measurement can occur due to cracks, uneven sample surface or wrong level of sample surface. Thus, it is crucial for the observer to have sufficient practice in producing smooth and level samples before taking measurements. Surface sampling also had high uncertainty, often due to difficulties in sampling very hard or soft snow. Additionally, the snow surface may comprise multiple layers within the topmost 2.5 cm, and the uncertainty for repeated surface samples could arise from a different ratio of snow types in the sample, especially when the sample is corrected for smoothness and level with the addition of more snow using a spatula. In this study, majority of the samples were obtained using the spatula, ensuring that the sample level is not lower than the sample holder. However, when using the sampler on soft snow, there is a potential for the sample to be too low. Future investigations could include effects of both too low or high sample levels.

In Sodankylä, the uncertainty from the orientation of the sample under the laser was greater than in Antarctica, which could be attributed to observed grain size according to Domine et al. (2006). Rotation had the most significant impact on measurements for surface snow, hard snow, wet snow or if the sample includes snow from layer interfaces. It's worth noting that not all experiments involved rotating the samples. Consequently, results obtained from other studies such as sampling at the same height or surface sampling might be influenced by uncertainties arising from the sample's orientation under the laser.

The uncertainty from repeating sampling at the same height was somewhat higher for Sodankylä than for Antarctica, potentially due to error sources from sampling such as mechanical destruction of the grain structure, which is grain type dependent (Martin and Schneebeli, 2023), or other difficulties in sampling grain types present in Sodankylä. Nevertheless, it is important to acknowledge that observed differences could also arise from spatial variability. The highest RSTD was noted for repeating sampling of wet snow.

Potential melting at observed temperatures had only a minor impact in both regions, so it's more important to prepare the sample carefully than to produce it quickly. The most significant impact of potential melting (11% for maximum values) was observed in the case of wet snow. However, it's important to recognize that measurements may generally encompass the possibility of error due to sample melting. Conversely, it's crucial to ascertain whether the sample began melting during the sampling process to appropriately apply the equation for wet snow SSA.

Selecting the initial or final calibration, when successful, had a negligible impact on the results when significant temperature changes had not occurred. However, it's crucial to emphasize that recalibration is essential if the air temperature has changed during the measurement session (Zuanon, 2013). Particularly, when the instrument is used over extended periods, recalibration midway through the process is advisable due to the increased likelihood of significant air temperature fluctuations.

According to the instrument manufacturer, IceCube provides SSA measurements with an accuracy of 10% within the range 2–130 m²/kg. Measurements employed in this study fell below 50 m²/kg. According to the instrument manual, error may arise from several factors, including operating the instrument immediately after a brutal temperature change, exposing the instrument or tools to direct sunlight in temperatures near 0 °C, working in rainy conditions, insufficient acclimation time (less than 20 min) in new temperature conditions, unstable calibration after a temperature change or device restart, dirty calibration standards, incorrect positioning of calibration standards or snow samples in the snow port, imperfect leveling of the sample with the sample holder, non-flat sample surface, sample inhomogeneity related to light penetration depth, loose and broken snow particles on the sample surface from cutting with spatula, presence of large depth hoar crystals, inadequate compaction for very light fresh snow, sample melting or contamination due to waiting time before measurement, incorrect information on calibration standards in the software, calibration quality issues, incorrect input of calibration values or signal values into the software, and dust accumulation in the integrating sphere. Hence, it is crucial to follow instructions outlined in the manual to minimize potential errors.

Gallet et al. (2009) concluded that the uncertainty of SSA determination using infrared hemispherical reflectance at 1310 nm is 10% for SSA values below 60 m²/kg. They identified random and systematic error sources, as presented in Table 2. Conversely, according to a modelling study by Picard et al. (2009), hemispherical reflectance can vary by 25% for a given SSA due to changes in crystal shape.

In this study, some observed uncertainty sources were small in comparison to the instrument's accuracy. However, insufficient sample preparation can lead up to a 45% increase in errors. In most cases observed in this study, uncertainties remained below 25% threshold associated with crystal shape variations. In conclusion, the findings underline the critical role of sample preparation in ensuring reliable SSA measurements. These results enhance the estimation of measurement precision for future applications.

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Table 2
Error sources for DUFISSS defined by Gallet et al. (2009).

Type	Source	Magnitude
Random error	The reflectance standards	0.6% (determined by the manufacturer)
	An individual SSA measurement using CH ₄ adsorption	6% (Legagneux et al., 2002)
	The calibration curve	4%
	A reflectance measurement	1%
	Crystal shape	3%
	Polynomial fit for SSA and reflectance, and equation for taking density into account	Less than 1%
Systematic error	CH ₄ adsorption method	5% or less based on Legagneux et al. (2002) and Kerbrat et al. (2008)

albedo, snow surface roughness” (LAS3R) [335986, 2020], and by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under project “Drivers and Feedbacks of Changes in Arctic Terrestrial Biodiversity (CHARTER)” [869471, 2020].

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Leena Leppänen: Formal analysis, Investigation, Visualization, Writing – original draft.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Leena Leppänen reports financial support, administrative support, and equipment, drugs, or supplies were provided by Finnish Meteorological Institute. Leena Leppänen reports financial support was provided by University of Lapland. Leena Leppänen reports a relationship with Finnish Meteorological Institute that includes: employment, non-financial support, and travel reimbursement. Leena Leppänen reports a relationship with University of Lapland that includes: employment, non-financial support, and travel reimbursement.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coldregions.2023.104105>.

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